

Renewable Energy Communities in Sweden: A Techno-Economic Analysis of Single-Owner, Multiple-Consumer Building-Level Energy Sharing

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Abstract

Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) are evolving as key enablers of climate action and renewable energy integration. However, they face technical and economic challenges, particularly in energy allocation, pricing structures and stakeholder expertise. Existing studies primarily focus on multi-owner RECs, overlooking single-owner models – increasingly relevant in urban settings. This study analyzes a real-world single-owner REC, comparing hourly- and monthly-based pricing models and four energy allocation strategies using techno-economic metrics. Results show that hourly-based pricing reduces costs but lowers revenues. Furthermore, allocation strategies minimally impact technical performance in such REC setting. While the differences between the strategies themselves are negligible from the landlord's perspective, the impacts on tenants in terms of cost distribution and fairness could vary, requiring further investigation.

Key Innovations

- Moves beyond multi-owner REC models by analyzing a single-owner setup in which the building owner manages energy generation, sales, and allocation between multiple consumers and the grid.
- Hybrid Allocation Strategy: Combines equal and proportional distribution to evaluate cost-effectiveness and operational efficiency in RECs.

Practical Implications

This study provides practical insights for optimizing single-owner RECs. The findings offer a scalable framework for landlords, policymakers, and energy service providers to improve financial viability, enhance operational efficiency, and encourage tenant engagement, supporting informed decision-making in urban energy-sharing models.

Introduction

The European Directive RED-II (European Parliament and Council, 2018) aimed at promoting renewable energy, introduced Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) – a framework transforming relationships between end-users and the energy sector. An energy community consists of geographically close producers, consumers, and prosumers engaged in local energy exchange. Voluntary participation, openness, and democratic governance are fundamental principles in RECs. Depending on national regulations, RECs are sometimes interchangeably

referred to as Collective Self-Consumption (CSC), but the terms are not synonymous. CSC involves multiple consumers – typically within the same building or local grid – jointly utilizing local renewable energy to maximize self-consumption. In contrast, RECs are broader entities that can encompass CSC but also extend to energy trading, flexibility services, and active participation in the electricity market (Di Silvestre et al., 2021). They focus exclusively on renewable energy, engaging in generation, aggregation, distribution, trading, consumption, and storage (European Commission, 2024). By integrating solar PV, wind, and energy storage solutions, RECs reduce fossil fuel dependence and support energy transition policies (Backe et al., 2022). Their support for flexibility mechanisms, such as demand-side response and storage, improves local supply-demand balance, reducing curtailment losses and system costs (García & Weber, 2023).

Problem Statement

Advancing RECs faces challenges due to limited technical expertise among participants. Many small-scale RECs are managed by individuals lacking knowledge of electrical systems, limiting their ability to navigate market dynamics (Lazdins et al., 2021). Consequently, RECs encounter technical, economic, and regulatory barriers, as existing frameworks often fail to support decentralized energy systems (Yaqoot et al., 2016). Economic viability depends on maximizing self-consumption and minimizing grid reliance, yet REC benefits largely hinge on effective design and management (Di Silvestre et al., 2021). Research has predominantly focused on multi-owner or cooperative-driven RECs (Silva et al., 2023; Verbruggen et al., 2023), overlooking the common urban case of multi-apartment buildings owned by a single landlord. A single-owner REC model – where one entity manages generation, distribution, and cost allocation – could mitigate some of these challenges by simplifying market participation and enabling professional energy management. This study explores single-owner RECs, focusing on optimizing energy allocation, cost-effectiveness, and billing structures. It analyzes a real-world municipal REC, where a municipality-owned company manages a multifamily building, acting as both community manager and prosumer – producing, selling, and consuming electricity while distributing energy among tenants and the grid. The study examines the technical and economic implications from the owner's perspective, rather than that of the tenants.

Study Objectives

This study investigates how different energy allocation strategies impact the cost-effectiveness and operational efficiency of a single-owner REC under dynamic market pricing conditions. To achieve this, our analysis focuses on two key objectives:

- **Evaluation of dynamic hourly market pricing for** grid imports, exports, and tenant sales to evaluate cost-effectiveness and revenue optimization under hourly market.
- **Comparative Evaluation of Energy Allocation Strategies** by comparing the performance of the real-world energy allocation strategy currently used in the case study against four alternative strategies to determine potential improvements in cost savings, operational efficiency, and financial viability.

By addressing these objectives, this study provides a structured framework for designing and managing single-owner RECs, offering practical insights for policymakers, real estate owners, and energy service providers in urban energy-sharing models.

Methods

Our method consists of analyzing monthly versus hourly electricity pricing impacts on cost savings and revenues, both for the real-world case in Hus 1A and a fully grid-reliant scenario. We then conducted a techno-economic evaluation of the actual system using operational data from 2024 and a set of technical and economic performance metrics. Finally, we simulated four alternative energy allocation strategies and performed a techno-economic comparison of their effects on system performance and financial outcomes. This section outlines the metrics, case study data, scenario definitions, and allocation strategies used in this study.

Literature Review

Through our review of the literature, we identified the critical importance of analyzing cost savings, revenues, and operational performance in RECs. Additionally, we identified a growing body of research on the profitability and viability of shared energy systems, particularly concerning photovoltaics (PV) integration, energy sharing and trading mechanisms, and dynamic electricity pricing models and their impact. Similar studies have analyzed key economic indicators, including energy cost savings and revenues (Huang et al., 2022), and dynamic pricing models that enhance market efficiency and cost optimization through demand-side management strategies (Hashemnezhad et al., 2024; Mota et al., 2024). In terms of technical indicators, important metrics such as self-sufficiency, self-consumption (Fournely et al., 2024; Simiou et al., 2024), grid dependency, and production-to-load ratio (Viti et al., 2020) have been examined to assess the sustainability and efficiency of RECs, along with some discussions about environmental and social fairness metrics. Collectively, this literature review informed our metric selection, the integration of dynamic pricing models, and the design of multiple allocation strategies, with a focus on two key dimensions: cost savings and

operational efficiency – both of which are shown to be critical in REC implementation and optimization.

Technical Performance Metrics

To assess the technical performance of the REC, five key metrics are utilized:

1. **Self-Sufficiency** measures the extent to which on-site renewable generation meets the building's total energy demand.
2. **Self-Consumption** evaluates the proportion of generated renewable energy that is consumed within the building rather than exported to the grid, highlighting the efficiency of local energy use (Fournely et al., 2022; Simoiu et al., 2022).
3. **Grid Dependency** measures the share of total energy demand met by external electricity imports, indicating the degree of autonomy achieved through on-site generation (Bokkisam and Selvan, 2021; Abdelhameed et al., 2024).
4. **Production-to-Load Ratio** assesses whether the REC produces enough energy to sustain itself, generates excess energy for export, or falls shorter requiring greater reliance on imported electricity (Viti et al., 2020).
5. **Renewable Energy Share** quantifies the share of energy demand met by renewable energy. In our case, it accounts for the solar energy produced by the building, in addition to the portion of imported electricity classified as renewable (49% as per the owner's agreement with the electricity provider).

Economic Performance Metrics

The Energy Cost Savings and Revenue metrics compare total energy costs and gains under the REC model, quantifying direct financial benefits from the landlord's perspective (Huang et al., 2022; Mustika et al., 2023). These metrics are essential for evaluating the economic viability of RECs and their potential to enhance affordability and profitability for all stakeholders (Huang et al., 2022). To improve the accuracy of economic assessments, this study incorporates dynamic electricity market prices sourced from the Nord Pool SE3 market zone (Nord Pool Group, 2024), capturing hourly fluctuations in electricity rates. These data were processed using Python and Excel to match hourly energy consumption and production profiles. The dynamic pricing model enabled a realistic evaluation of cost savings, revenue from surplus energy exports to the grid and sales to tenants, and the overall financial viability of REC operations under varying market conditions.

Case Study and Data Collection

Our analysis focuses on a single residential building in Skogstorp, Sweden (Figure 1). The building owner, who also serves as the Community Manager (CM) and prosumer, operates the energy system by generating electricity through rooftop PV panels, supplemented by grid imports. This electricity is used to cover the building's operational needs – including hallway lighting, shared amenities, elevators, door systems, ventilation, and occasional backup heating – as well as to supply the

tenants. Any surplus generation is sold to the grid after meeting both building operational and tenant demands.

Figure 1: Case study site, with Hus 1A as the primary focus. The methodology and findings can also be applicable to Hus 1B and Hus 2B in the same complex.

The tenants' electricity consumption analyzed in this study pertains to their energy use of household appliances such as refrigerators, TVs, washing machines, and other devices. Heating and hot water costs are included in the rent, as they are supplied by the central heating system (Table 1) and supplemented by the building's operational energy consumption. To ensure a realistic representation of the system studied in this paper, we collected technical and historical energy and financial data for the full calendar year of 2024, covering the parameters listed in Tables 1 and 2. Additionally, we incorporate key cost inputs derived from the real energy bills, detailing the pricing model and billing structure, grid and transmission fees, internal electricity provider pricing, and other relevant components (Table 3). The consumption data for all 23 apartments in the building, along with the building's operational consumption profile are shown in Figure 2.

Table 1: Technical specifications of Hus 1A.

Feature	Details
Number of Apartments	23 Apartments
Building Area (A-temp)	1519 m ²
Installed Solar PV Capacity	45 kWp
Total Solar Production/year (kWh)	44,987 kWh
Total Surplus Exported/year (kWh)	13,775 kWh
Total Solar Self-Consumed (kWh)	31,212 kWh
Total Energy Consumption/year	95,692 kWh
Total Energy Imported from Grid	64,480 kWh
Imported Energy Source	49% Renewable, 51% Nuclear
Heating System	Ground Source Heat Pump
Additional Heating (Backup)	Electric Backup

Table 1: Collected energy data for Hus 1A.

Data Collected
Hourly Solar Production (kWh)
Solar Surplus Exported to Grid (kWh)
Hourly Solar Self-Consumption (kWh)
Hourly Total Consumption (Solar + Grid import) (kWh)
Hourly Apartments' Consumption (kWh)
Hourly Building Operational Consumption (kWh)
Hourly Import from Grid (kWh)
Dynamic Market Price SE3 (SEK/kWh)
Electricity Bill from the Grid (SEK)
Bill to the Tenants (SEK)
Bill to Grid for Exported Surplus (SEK)

Table 3. Breakdown of electricity bill components with Euro equivalents (May 2025 rate: 1 SEK = 0.09 EUR).

Charge Type	Unit Price (EUR, excl. VAT)	Unit
Fixed Fee	18.00	Per month (28–31 days)
Electricity Transmission Fee	0.0099	Per kWh
Monthly Maximum Power Fee	variable	Per kW
Administrative Fee	0.009	Per kWh
Electricity Spot Price (SEK/kWh, SE3)	variable	Per kWh
Production Transmission Credit	0.0036	Per kWh fed into the grid
Production Revenue	variable	Per kWh sold to the grid
National Grid Fee	0.0016	Per kWh
VAT (Moms 25%) Applied	25%	Applied to all charges

Figure 1: Total Monthly Building Consumption.

Weighted Proportional Allocation

Since hourly data on solar self-consumption or production was not available – only daily, monthly, and yearly values were provided – we prioritized consistency with the real-world dataset rather than relying on simulated profiles. To align with the hourly resolution used in the broader analysis, we applied a Weighted Proportional Allocation (WPA) method, using the available hourly surplus export as a reference factor. This method assumes that the distribution of exported surplus energy reflects the

underlying solar self-consumption pattern. Specifically, each hour's share of the total daily surplus export was calculated and used as a weighting factor to disaggregate the total daily self-consumption into hourly values. The weighted proportional allocation equation for estimating hourly solar self-consumption $C_{h,d}$ based on hourly surplus export $S_{h,d}$ as a weighting factor can be expressed as follows:

$$C_{h,d} = \left(\frac{S_{h,d}}{\sum_{h=1}^{24} S_{h,d}} \right) \times C_d \quad (1)$$

$C_{h,d}$ = Estimated self-consumption at hour h on day d

$S_{h,d}$ = Surplus export at hour h on day d

C_d = Total known solar self-consumption for the entire day d

$\sum_{h=1}^{24} S_{h,d}$ = Total surplus export for the entire day d

$\frac{S_{h,d}}{\sum S_{h,d}}$ = represents the hourly weighting factor, ensuring that the allocation follows the observed surplus export pattern.

Scenario Definition

In this study, we compare two overarching scenarios to assess the feasibility and impact of implementing a REC in a single-owner setting with different allocation strategies and pricing models (monthly versus hourly based pricing model):

- **Business with no REC scenario (NREC):** This scenario models a building that is fully reliant on grid imports, with no renewable generation or storage. It serves as a baseline for comparison with the real-world case study, enabling an assessment of technical and economic performance, as well as the cost-effectiveness of monthly versus hourly market pricing.
- **Real-World Case Study (RWCS):** The RWCS represents the actual operational case where all energy-related bills and costs follow a monthly-based pricing model, covering electricity imported from the grid, electricity sales to tenants, and other associated costs, fees, and revenues. A specific agreement with the grid provider ensures that 70–75% of imported electricity is contracted at a fixed monthly average price for a specified period, while the remaining 25–30% is subject to dynamic market pricing based on Nord Pool SE3 (Nord Pool Group, 2024). Additionally, an administrative fee of 0.10 SEK/kWh is applied when billing tenants. To fully assess system efficiency, solar production revenues, and energy cost, we have collected and analyzed all electricity bills from 2024, including pricing structures, taxes, and additional fees, as detailed in Table 3. RWCS is also evaluated under an alternative hourly-based market pricing model to examine its economic feasibility and impact on financial and operational performance.

Energy Allocation Strategies

- Within the RWCS framework, the study evaluates four alternative energy allocation strategies (**EAS1-EAS4**):

EAS1 - Proportional to Consumption (Load-Based Allocation) which distributes energy based on each tenant's electricity demand, ensuring that higher-consuming users receive a larger share of the available renewable energy. As described by Gianaroli et al. (2024) and Ogando-Martínez et al. (2023), it optimizes energy self-consumption by aligning allocations with demand.

EAS2 - Equal Distribution (Uniform-Based Allocation) which ensures shared renewable energy is evenly divided among all participants based on the minimum user's consumption value, regardless of consumption levels (Gianaroli et al., 2024; Ogando-Martínez et al., 2023).

EAS3 - Pearson Correlation-Based Allocation which prioritizes tenants whose consumption patterns closely align with solar energy generation. The allocation is determined using the Pearson correlation coefficient, where users with demand profiles that match renewable production peaks receive a larger share of energy. This approach incentivizes demand-side flexibility and enhances overall system efficiency, as described in Gianaroli et al. (2024).

EAS4 - Hybrid Fixed-Dynamic Allocation. This strategy is inspired by the hybrid approach proposed by Gianaroli et al. (2024), which combines correlation-based and trend-based methods to improve operational efficiency by directing surplus renewable energy toward users whose consumption patterns align with generation. This minimizes losses and enhances self-consumption. While the inspiration stems from their hybrid concept, the specific combination used in our study is our own adaptation. We allocate 50% of the shared energy equally among all participants, while the remaining 50% is distributed proportionally based on each member's total consumption. The equal-share component is intended to promote fairness and inclusiveness, while also supporting financial predictability and stakeholder acceptance within the REC framework.

Results

Comparing Monthly vs. Hourly-Based Pricing in NREC and RWCS

Before assessing the broader impact of implementing a REC, we first examine how different electricity pricing structures affect a fully grid-dependent building (NREC) and an energy community with on-site solar generation (RWCS). This comparison helps determine whether pricing models alone can influence cost savings and revenue generation. For NREC, switching from monthly-based pricing to hourly-based pricing could lead to a 24.4% reduction in total annual energy costs, resulting in savings of approximately 2,606 EUR per year, or an average of 215 EUR per month, as shown in Table 4. However, while hourly pricing can provide substantial cost savings due to lower market prices at certain times, the stability and predictability of monthly-based pricing

may still be preferred, depending on stakeholders' risk tolerance and prevailing energy market conditions.

Table 4: NREC hourly vs monthly based pricing.

Metric	Hourly-Based Pricing (Hypothetical)	Monthly-Based Pricing (Real Case Study)	Difference
Total Cost Incl. VAT	7,968	10,574	-2,606
Average Monthly Cost	664	879	-215

For RWCS, we compare the existing monthly pricing model with an alternative hourly-based pricing model under the same conditions. As shown in Table 5, the monthly-based pricing model generates approximately 362 EUR (46.6%) more revenue than the hourly-based pricing for selling solar to tenants, primarily because it relies on a stable SE3 market price, which remains higher than the average hourly price during peak solar production. In contrast, hourly pricing fluctuates, often leading to lower revenues when solar generation coincides with low market prices. However, when considering imported energy costs, the hourly-based model results in 406 EUR in cost savings compared to the monthly-based pricing, as shown in Table 6. Despite earning 42 EUR less in revenue from surplus energy sales to the grid, the hourly-based approach achieves overall net savings of 364 EUR per year. Thus, hourly-based pricing proves more cost-effective for imported energy, while monthly-based pricing is more profitable for solar energy sales to tenants and to the grid. The choice between the two depends on whether the priority is minimizing energy costs or maximizing solar revenue.

Table 5: Revenues from selling solar energy to tenants.

Pricing Model	Total Revenue After VAT (EUR)
Hourly-Based Pricing	777
Monthly-Based Pricing	1,139
Difference	+362 (Monthly-Based Pricing is Higher)

Table 6: Costs and revenues with grid interaction.

Metric	Hourly-Based Pricing (EUR)	Monthly-Based Pricing (EUR)	Better Option
Total Cost	6,917	7,323	Hourly-Based (saves 406 EUR)
Revenues from Selling to grid	179	221	Monthly-Based (higher by 42 EUR)
Net Cost (Cost - Revenue)	6,738	7,102	Hourly-Based (saves 364 EUR)

RWCS Assessment

While the pricing analysis reveals the impacts on costs and revenues, assessing RWCS's viability requires examining its technical and economic performance, including self-consumption, grid dependency, and energy allocation. By analyzing the real data, RWCS achieves an annual self-consumption rate of 69.38% (Table 7), meaning nearly 70% of the solar energy generated was consumed on-site, while the remaining surplus was exported to the grid. This resulted in an annual self-sufficiency rate of 32.62%, indicating that solar energy covered approximately one-third of the building's total yearly consumption, reducing annual grid dependency to 67.38%. Since the imported grid mix consists of 49% renewable and 51% nuclear energy, on-site solar consumption increased the total annual renewable energy share to 65.63%. Additionally, the annual production-to-load ratio of 47% suggests that, under optimal conditions, solar production could potentially cover nearly half of the building's yearly energy demand. Economically, the RWCS model achieved significant cost savings compared to NREC, lowering annual electricity costs from 10,573 EUR to 7,324 EUR, a total reduction of 3,251 EUR. Additionally, selling surplus electricity back to the grid generated 262 EUR in production revenue, with an additional 55 EUR earned from transmission credits, bringing the total revenue from exported surplus to 317 EUR. Furthermore, selling solar energy directly to tenants generated 1,090 EUR, leading to a total combined revenue of 1,408 EUR from both surplus grid exports and tenant sales. These findings underscore the economic, technical, and to some extent, environmental benefits of implementing RECs compared to a fully grid-dependent scenario, demonstrating both cost reductions and an increased share of renewable energy utilization.

Table 7: Energy Performance and Cost Summary NREC vs RWCS.

Metric	Value
Self-Consumption Rate (%)	69.38
Self-Sufficiency Rate (%)	32.62
Grid Dependency (%)	67.38
Renewable Energy Share (%)	65.63
Production-to-Load Ratio (%)	47
Electricity Cost with Solar (EUR)	7,323
Electricity Cost without Solar (EUR)	10,574
Cost Savings (EUR)	3,251
Production Revenue from selling to Grid (EUR)	262
Transmission Credit for exported surplus (EUR)	55
Total Revenue from Surplus exported to grid (EUR)	317
Revenue from Selling to Tenants (EUR)	1,090
Total Revenue (Surplus + Tenants) (EUR)	1,408

Comparing four allocation strategies EAS1 - EAS4

The comparison between the four proposed EAS and RWCS across the technical and economic metrics are shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4 respectively. RWCS has a self-sufficiency rate of around 32%, which is consistent across the other allocation strategies, indicating that none of the suggested EAS significantly impact self-sufficiency, and the community is still heavily dependent on the grid for energy supply, with grid dependency fluctuating around 70%. On the other hand, self-consumption is maintained at a high level (~70%) in all cases, which means the available solar energy is effectively utilized within the community.

Figure 3: Technical Performance Comparison between RWCS and the four different EASs.

Figure 4: Economic Performance Comparison between RWCS and the four different EASs.

The renewable energy share remains nearly the same across all EAS, slightly above 65%. This suggests that the total share of renewable energy in the system is constrained by existing infrastructure, and EAS alone are not significantly shifting this metric. The suggested EASs do not significantly improve the technical performance compared to the RWCS. However, the comparison of the economic metrics (Figure 4) shows that all EASs reduce electricity costs (from buying from the grid) compared to the RWCS. This reduction is mainly due to the hourly pricing model used in these strategies, compared to the monthly-based pricing model in RWCS – as shown by the analysis done in Table 6. The revenue from exporting surplus to the grid for the EASs increases between 17.5% and 20% compared to the RWCS. This revenue stream is quite low compared to other metrics (e.g. revenue from selling to tenants), and the variation among the EASs is minimal. On the other hand, the revenue from selling

energy to tenants is considerably higher in EASs compared to RWCS – increasing by approximately 120% – and also higher than surplus export revenue. This indicates that prioritizing selling energy to tenants is more profitable than exporting to the grid. Overall, while all EASs demonstrate clear economic benefits over RWCS, the differences among them remain minimal, suggesting that the choice of a specific EAS has a relatively small impact on cost savings and revenue generation from the landlord perspective.

Discussion

The results clearly demonstrate that cost savings and revenues can be quantified, offering insights for similar studies. Specifically, our analysis shows that implementing a REC (RWCS) resulted in 30% cost savings compared to a fully grid-dependent building (NREC), while revenue varied more significantly with the pricing model than with the allocation strategy. However, these financial outputs are not standalone indicators of profitability; they are shaped by external factors such as investment costs, financial incentives, tax reductions, and regulatory frameworks. One critical determinant of profitability is the balance between capital expenditure (CAPEX) and operational expenditure (OPEX), as explored by Trevisan et al. (2022). These factors directly affect the Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE), a key economic metric examined by Faria et al. (2023). A lower LCOE improves the competitiveness of on-site solar energy and influences the sale price, ultimately shaping profitability. Our findings show that selling solar energy to tenants yields higher revenues than exporting surplus to the grid. However, this is not automatically the more profitable option, as on-site energy sharing may involve higher CAPEX for batteries, smart meters, and related infrastructure, along with increased OPEX. Additionally, the potential to implement favorable solar energy pricing, distinct from imported electricity rates, should be further explored in future research to support long-term economic feasibility and greater renewable energy penetration.

Our findings also indicate that allocation strategies alone do not significantly affect the technical performance metrics analyzed in this study. This may partly be due to the analysis being conducted from the building owner's perspective. However, when combined with differentiated pricing schemes and various incentives, allocation strategies may have a stronger impact for tenants, particularly in shaping their electricity costs. For example, a Pearson correlation-based allocation may benefit tenants who align consumption with solar peaks, whereas proportional allocation could favor high-energy users. These differences raise in turn concerns about fairness, as certain strategies might optimize savings for specific tenants while creating pricing disparities for others. Future research should explore tenant-centric optimization models that balance economic efficiency and fairness, dynamic pricing, and policy interventions to ensure equitable cost distribution in such REC setups.

We acknowledge that the WPA method used in this study is based on assumptions that would not be necessary if

real hourly self-consumption data were available. However, the central aim of this study – to evaluate the cost-effectiveness and operational performance of monthly versus hourly pricing models alongside a comparison of four energy allocation strategies – does not critically depend on exact hourly load profiles. Moreover, although a battery system was installed, it remained inactive and disconnected from both internal operations and the electricity market during the analysis period (up to mid-2025). As such, it had no effect on self-consumption or surplus exports. Had it been active, it would likely have influenced both consumption dynamics and export patterns. Therefore, the WPA method was considered sufficient to meet the study's objectives. Future research should examine how active battery dispatch might impact allocation strategies, enhance self-consumption, enable grid services such as peak shaving and frequency regulation, and improve overall REC profitability. For this study, however, the method represents a justified and pragmatic compromise for generating robust comparative insights.

Finally, it is important to contextualize this case study within the broader EU definition of RECs as outlined in the European Directive RED-II. RECs are characterized by voluntary participation, democratic governance, autonomy, and prioritization of environmental and social benefits over profit. While these principles are recognized in the literature, most real-world projects only partially reflect the full REC model. In our case, the setup closely resembles collective self-consumption, where locally generated energy is used within the same building. It also involves energy trading, as surplus is sold to both tenants and the grid. Although a battery system is present, it is not yet used to support self-consumption, peak shaving, or market participation, as REC principles might suggest. Another defining feature is the ownership structure: the REC is managed by a single municipal housing company rather than a cooperative. Legally and operationally, the owner functions similarly to a medium-sized business, controlling energy distribution within the community. However, this raises questions about tenant participation. In this setup, tenants have no alternative but to purchase electricity from the building owner, challenging the REC principles of democracy and voluntariness. While the REC may appear voluntary and democratic from the owner's perspective, these characteristics may not hold from the tenants' point of view. This discrepancy highlights an important research avenue focused on the social dimension of RECs, especially in single-owner models where tenants act as passive consumers rather than active participants in energy governance.

Conclusion

This study conducted a techno-economic analysis of a municipal single-owner Renewable Energy Community, evaluating four energy allocation strategies and two pricing models to assess their impact on cost-effectiveness and system operational efficiency. The findings highlight the economic and technical benefits of

transitioning from a fully grid-dependent model to a REC, demonstrating lower electricity costs, increased self-consumption, and reduced grid dependency. Additionally, the ability to generate revenue from both grid exports and tenant sales reinforces the financial viability of this approach. A key insight from the pricing model comparison is that monthly-based pricing generates higher revenues from solar energy sales due to the stability of SE3 market prices, which remain higher than average hourly prices during peak solar production. However, hourly-based pricing proves more cost-effective for imported energy, leading to 5.14% higher annual net savings despite slightly lower revenues from grid exports. Furthermore, the comparison of four energy allocation strategies (EAS1–EAS4) with the real-world case study (RWCS) reveals that allocation mechanisms alone do not significantly impact key technical and economic metrics. The observed economic differences stem from the pricing model rather than the allocation strategy itself. The renewable energy share remains stable suggesting that total renewable integration is primarily constrained by infrastructure rather than allocation methods. While these findings provide valuable insights for single-owner RECs, further research is needed to explore how allocation strategies interact with tenant electricity costs and fairness considerations. Finally, the study provides important insights into tenant participation and governance in single-owner RECs, highlighting the need for future research on policy frameworks that promote democratic engagement and equitable cost distribution.

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